

IMPACTS OF NANO TECHNOLOGY ON ENVIRONMENT- A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Nano scaled particles have relatively larger surface area per unit mass which is the critical factor to increase mechanical modulus and other physical and chemical properties. Nanotechnology increases the strengths of many materials and devices, as well as enhances efficiencies of monitoring devices, remediation of environmental pollution, and renewable energy production. In general, nano technology devices consume less energy, reduce material wastes, and helps in monitoring devices. Nanotechnology can also be used to reduce and prevent the toxicity of nanoparticles in environment more efficiently. Nanoparticles have higher surface areas than the bulk materials which can cause more damage to the human body and environment compared to the bulk particles. Therefore, concern for the potential risk to the society due to nanoparticles has attracted national and international attentions. The present paper discusses about the positive and negative impacts on nano – technology on man and environment.

Key Words: Nano Particles, Toxicity, Environment

Introduction:

‘Nanotechnology’ is the science of studying phenomena and the manipulation of materials at atomic, molecular and macromolecular scale. Use of the prefix ‘nano’ in this context refers to a nano metre (nm). A nanometer is one-billionth of a meter. A sheet of paper is about 1,00,000 nanometers thick; a single gold atom is about one third of a nanometer in diameter. Dimensions between approximately 1 and 100 nanometers are known as the ‘nanoscale’. Nanomaterials are generally defined as materials that are <100 nm (0.1 mm) at least one dimension. This means that nanomaterials can be three-dimensional particles of almost any shape, ultrathin films (two-dimensional-like) or fine rods (essentially one-dimensional).

Ecological Perspective:

Ecologists have good reason to believe that even this shape difference will play a big role in their environmental and specifically, their biological influences. But most importantly and far beyond this simple classification with respect to size, nanomaterials are so fascinating because their properties and therefore their environmental/biological behavior, depend on their size. This is to say that their chemical (reactivity, solubility etc), mechanical (elasticity, hardness etc), electronic (conductivity, redox behavior etc) and nuclear (magnetic) properties often change as a function of size. These changes can be and often are dramatic. Finally, through desertification, biomass burning, industrial combustion, engine exhaust, mining and other anthropogenic activities, humans have vastly increased the global supply and variety of incidental nanoparticles, that is those nanoparticles unintentionally produced by humans.

Role of Nano – Technology:

Nanotechnology has revolutionary changes in commerce will transform daily life of consumer products in many ways.

1. Nanotechnology has been heralded as a “revolution” in science, for two reasons: first, because of its revolutionary view of the way in which chemicals and elements, such as gold and silver, behave, compared to traditional scientific understanding of their properties. Second, the impact of these new discoveries, as applied to commerce, can transform the daily life of consumer products ranging from sun tan lotions to cosmetics, food packaging, paints and coatings for cars, housing and fabrics, medicine and thousands of industrial processes. Beneficial consumer use of nanotechnologies, already in the stream of commerce, improves coatings on inks and paints in everything from food packaging to car paintings.

2. Additionally, ‘Nano medicine’ offers the promise of diagnosis and treatment at the molecular level in order to detect and treat pre symptomatic disease or to rebuild neurons in Alzheimer’s and Parkinson’s disease. There is a possibility that severe complications such as stroke or heart attack may be avoided by means of prophylactic treatment of people at risk and bone regeneration may keep many people active who never expected rehabilitation. Miniaturizations of diagnostic equipment can also reduce the amount of sampling materials required for testing and medical surveillance.

3. Miraculous developments, that sound like science fiction to those people who eagerly anticipate these medical products, combined with the emerging commercial impact of nanotechnology applications to consumer products will reshape civil society - permanently. Thus, everyone within the jurisdiction of the Council of Europe is an end-user of nanotechnology, even without realizing that nanotechnology has touched daily life.

Engineered Nanoparticles:

Engineered nanoparticles are defined simply as any intentionally produced particle that has a characteristic dimension between 1 and 100 nm and possesses properties that are not shared by any nanoscale particles with the same chemical composition (USNTC, 2004). As a result of their small size, nanomaterials possess unique properties, this is particularly true for nanoparticles <20 to 30 nm in size, which are generally characterized as having an excess of energy at the particle surface that makes them highly reactive and thermodynamically unstable (Auffan et al., 2009). Those nanomaterials that have the most unique characteristics (e.g., the fluorescence properties of quantum dots, the tensile strength of Carbon NanoTubes [CNTs], the photocatalytic properties of TiO₂) have proven to be the most economically profitable (Wiesner et al., 2009).

Number of laboratory trials have measured acute toxicity and sublethal effects of Engineered Nano Particles (ENPs) on organisms (Kahru and Dubourguier, 2009). Yet, the absence of evidence should not be taken as proof that environmental impacts will not occur. As a community, ecologists are primed to be concerned about the consequences of new technologies for the environment. One need only mention asbestos, tetraethyl lead, DDT and PCBs or chlorofluorocarbons to conjure up the lung disease, lead poisoning, bird population declines, contaminated fisheries, and Antarctic ozone hole environmental disasters caused by these technological innovations (Rattner, 2009; Rowland, 1991).

Scientists recognize that Engineered Nano Particles (ENPs) can enter the environment directly through intentional environmental additions (e.g., zero-valent Fe for remediation [Yantasee et al., 2007]) or unintentional spills: (i) as the waste byproducts of ENP manufacture; (ii) through the liquid waste stream as they are leached from industrial and consumer products; (iii) as constituents of solid wastes from bio solids; and (iv) through landfill leaching of disposed products or bio solids.

Once ENPs enter the environment, their impact on organisms will be mediated by abiotic reactions that influence their solubility, shape and chemistry. Engineered nanoparticles that remain soluble or that are in high concentrations in the environment are more likely to have (i) direct effects on the organisms they encounter. Engineered nanoparticles may also (ii) indirectly affect organisms by altering the chemical environment or by (iii) increasing or decreasing the solubility, transport, or membrane transfer of

co-occurring contaminants. Regardless of whether any organism experiences lethal or sub lethal effects, if the ENP is incorporated into tissues or into detritus it is susceptible to trophic transfer and bioaccumulation into higher trophic levels.

Positive Impacts:

Nanotechnology increases the strengths of many materials and devices, as well as enhances efficiencies of monitoring devices, consumes less energy, reduces material waste, prevents toxicity, remediation of environmental pollution, and renewable energy production. While these are considered to be the positive effect of nanotechnology. The use of nanomaterials and nanoparticles can also lead to significant savings in resources and efficiency increases in manufacturing and energy related applications

Nanotechnology offers potential economic, societal and environment benefits. It has the potential to help reduce the human footprint on the environment by providing solutions for energy consumption, pollution, and green gas emissions.

Nanotechnology holds the promise of meeting global challenges of the twenty-first century regarding providing alternative energy, protecting the human right to clean water, ensuring wildlife protection, clean-up of brownfields and reducing the global disease burden.

It offers the potential for significant environmental benefits, including:

- Cleaner, more efficient industrial processes
- Improved ability to detect and eliminate pollution by improving air, water, and soil quality
- High precision manufacturing by reducing amount of waste
- Clean abundant power via more efficient solar cells
- Removal of greenhouse gases and other pollutants from the atmosphere
- Decreased need for large industrial plants
- Remediating environmental damages.

The nanoscale products that utilize graphene in an industrial use or research can benefit the environment in several ways:

- Graphene based nanocomposites reduce the weight of airplanes by substituting traditional metals and composites and the consequence of the weight saving results in a reduction of a thousand tons of gasoline.
- Graphene thin films or graphene buck papers can be substituted in place of metal meshes around the fuselage of airplane used to prevent the direct and indirect effects of lightning strikes.
- The eminent properties of graphene increase the efficiency of advanced renewable energy processes, such as reducing the weight of a wind turbine blades and increasing the energy converse efficiency.

Energy Consumption:

The use of graphene into a coating material resulting in the need for only one layer, which does not require a multifunctional film coating. Two applications for a graphene based coating are to apply it to a blade used in wind turbines or on the body of an airplane. It saves the weight increasing efficiency.

Cost Saving on Materials:

An alternative energy method such as hybrid automobiles will decrease the price by novel developments in nanotechnology.

Less Waste on Raw Materials:

Large sample testing will be done on a smaller scale and simultaneously use of raw materials will become more efficiency. Nanoscale chemical reagents (or catalysts) increase the reaction rate and other efficiency of chemical reactions.

Environmental Monitoring and Protection:

Utilizing advanced nanotechnology, a detector was made to detect a nuclear leak faster and more accurate at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant. Which is one of the best radiation detector in Washington and can sense the faintest amount of radiation.

Cheap and Clean Energy:

Prototype solar panels incorporating nanotechnology are more efficient than standard designs when converting sunlight into electricity. Nanotechnology is in use in batteries, nanomaterials may improve hydrogen storage materials and catalysts for fuel cells. By creating more surface area and lighter storage units, nanotechnology can enhance energy generation, conversion and storage for: fuel cell, solar cell, thermo-to-electric, biomass energy, hydrogen storage, secondary batteries, super-capacitors, and thermal storage fluids.

Protecting the human right to clean water:

Nanotechnology offers inexpensive water purification due to rapid, low cost impurity detection. Magnetic interactions using ultra small rust can help remove arsenic from drinking water.

Nanotechnology may also improve air and water quality monitoring, by developing more sensitive detection devices that can measure a broad range of pollutants and toxic agents simultaneously. Rapid detection allows for swift response, thereby minimizing damage and reducing remediation costs.

Clean-up of Brown Fields:

Antimicrobial properties of nano-silver may clean up oil spills and hazardous chemicals.

Pollution Reduction and Environmental Progress:

Lighter cars and machinery that require less fuel; alternative fuel and energy sources; and materials that detect and clean up environmental contaminants all seem possible. The University College of Dublin (UCD) Center for Bio-Nano Interactions (CBNI) studies the impact of nanoparticles dispersed in environmental milieu, where decaying plant and animal matter becomes natural organic matter, typically composed of polysaccharides, interact with nanoparticles, and examines how this interaction affects organic stability, dispersability, environmental fate and behavior.

Reducing the Global Disease Burden:

Improvements in health care through enhanced diagnosis and treatment will increase personal wellbeing worldwide.

Mitigating Economic Crisis

Investment in nanotechnology will stimulate economic growth that supports development of ancillary industries, such as marketing for new products, recycling and disposal of waste and litigation regarding: intellectual property and liability.

Applications:

Nanotechnology, which involves materials and processes on an ultra-small scale, is currently an area of intense scientific research due to the wide variety of potential applications in the biomedical, optical, and electronic fields. Nanotechnology can also provide solutions for certain environmental problems. Nevertheless, little is known about the potential impacts of nanoparticles on the environment and human health, even though in some cases chemical composition, shape and size have been shown to contribute to the toxicological effects. Nanoparticles can be beneficial in catalytic and remediation application.

Biological applications: Developing ultra-small probes on planetary surfaces for agricultural applications and control of soil, air, and water contamination.

Biomedical applications: This includes the medical diagnostic and treatments.

Polymer composite materials when compared to traditional structural materials made out of metals have a reduced weight, high specific modulus and high resistance to environmental effects.

Negative Impacts:

Nanoparticles have higher surface areas than the bulk materials which can cause more damage to the human body and environment compared to the bulk particles there are certain negative impacts of nanotechnology on environment in many ways, such as increased toxicological pollution on the environment due to the uncertain shape, size, and chemical compositions of some of the nanotechnology products (or nanomaterials). Carbon nanotubes appear to cause health effects similar to asbestos when they come into contact with lung epithelia (Poland et al., 2009), but it is less clear what effect Carbon Nano Tubes (CNTs) will have when they are present at low concentrations in soils, sediments, and natural waters.

Nano materials vary by shape and size which are important factors in determining the toxicity. Lack of information and methods of characterizing nanomaterials make existing technology extremely difficult to detect the nanoparticles in air for environmental protection. Also, information of the chemical structure is a critical factor to determine how toxic a nanomaterial is, and minor changes of chemical function group could drastically change its properties. Full risk assessment of the safety on human health and environmental impact need to be evaluated at all stages of nanotechnology. The risk assessment should include the exposure risk and its probability of exposure, toxicological analysis, transport risk, persistence risk, transformation risk and ability to recycle. Life cycle risk assessment is another factor that can be used to predict the environmental impacts.

As current nanoscale materials are becoming smaller, it is more difficult to detect toxic nanoparticles from waste which may contaminate the environment. There are few ways that nanoparticles or nanomaterials can become toxic and harm the surrounding environment:

- **Hydrophobic and Hydrophilic Nanoparticles:** Nano coating researchers are currently working on TiO₂ powder as a coating inclusion that will reduce the weathering effects, such as salt rain degradation on composite materials.

- **Mobility of Contaminants:** There are two general methods that nanoparticle can be emitted into atmosphere. Nanoparticles are emitted into air directly from the source called primary emission, and are the main source of the total emissions. However, secondary particles are emitted naturally, such as homogeneous nucleation with ammonia and sulfuric acid presents

Environmental Analysis :

Several nanoscale inclusions have been used for various applications. Among these nanoscale inclusions, graphene has the higher priority for various reasons. Graphene is one of the most advanced materials for structural improvement, substitution of silicon for electronic devices, as well as thermal transferring, and fire retardant.

Environmental Effects & Risks:

The risks associated with current consumer and industrial uses remain unknown and therefore unquantified. CBNI has begun research regarding plants, animals, and micro-organisms in order to understand the potential impact of nanoparticles upon ecosystems.

Environmental effects and risks associated with nanotechnology is very limited and inconsistent. The potential environmental harm through nanotechnology can be summarized as follows:

- High energy requirements for synthesizing nanoparticles causing high energy demand
- Dissemination of toxic, persistent nano substances originating environmental harm
- Lower recovery and recycling rates
- Environmental implications of other life cycle stages also not clear
- Lack of trained engineers and workers causing further concerns.

Graphene has outstanding properties and its products can benefit the environment and economy; unfortunately, graphene based composites may also harm the environment in other ways:

The toxic property of graphene is unknown, and is difficult to remove graphene from waste.

- Graphene could react with materials and biological systems in environment in a way that is unexpected.
- Graphene has a good thermal conductivity, and fire retardancy of the polymer nanocomposites is already well researched. However, scientists warn that it may cause fire risk if graphene is contaminated with other substances during the process.

DISCUSSION:

Ecological research on ENPs can take advantage of the wealth of oceanic, terrestrial, and atmospheric earth science research involving naturally occurring nanoparticles. In particular, there are significant physical and chemical similarities between the most widely manufactured ENPs and naturally occurring nanoparticles, although in a number of cases the exact size, shape, and

coatings/surface functional groups may be quite different from ENPs. Also, while the term *nanoparticle* may not yet be widely used in ecology, earth scientists have been studying at least some major classes of natural nanoparticles for many decades.

This is because an exceptionally wide variety of nanoparticles exist on earth, and are in fact ubiquitous in both the biotic and abiotic compartments of earth (Gilbert and Banfield, 2005; Hochella et al., 2008). The most abundant of these particles include ash from volcanoes and forest fires, sea salt aerosols, and the iron and other transition metal oxides in soils, rivers, and oceans (Hochella, 2008; Buseck and Adachi, 2008; Kulmala and Kerminen, 2008; Hassellöv and von der Kammer, 2008; and references therein). It has also been demonstrated that naturally occurring nanoparticles have important local, regional, and even global consequences. (Chadwick et al., 1999; Jickells et al., 2005; Prospero, 1999; Simonson, 1995). We now know that naturally occurring nanoparticles are even present in interplanetary and interstellar space (Hochella, 2008). They have also been abundant on earth since its formation, were part of its formation (Becker et al., 2006), and life from the beginning has evolved in their presence. Emerging research is suggesting that many organisms synthesize nanomaterials. Bacteria in sediments may synthesize electrically conductive pilli, called nanowires, for sensing neighbors or for transferring electrons and energy (Blango and Mulvey, 2009; Gorby et al., 2006). Bacterial reduction of uranyl, U⁶⁺(aq), to U(IV) oxide (uraninite) is an important bioremediation strategy (Bargar et al., 2008). Manceau et al. (2008) found that wetland plants, or their symbionts, synthesize copper (Cu) nanoparticles in their rooting zone when grown in contaminated soils, thereby reducing Cu uptake. As analytical tools for the detection of nanoparticles improves, that biogenic nanoparticles are ubiquitous and bio geochemically vital across the living planet. Multiple characteristics contribute to the toxicity of many nanomaterials; they include not just mass or number of particles but also the shape of the particles, the electrical charge at the particle surface, the coating of the particle with another material and numerous other characteristics.

Conclusion:

There is no doubt that nanotechnology will continue to be developed, be a benefit to society and improve the environment in various ways. Nanoscale materials will make the products better in terms of functionality, weight savings, less energy consumption and a cleaner environment. Shortcomings always exist when new unproven technology is released. Nanomaterial may help clean certain environmental wastes, but contaminate environment in other ways. Choosing the right nanoscale materials is one of the key parameters for the future direction of nanotechnology. Engineering ethics need to be defined before the commercial use of nanotechnology. Risk assessment on new nanomaterial based application is important to evaluate potential risk to our environment when the products are in use. Full life cycle evaluation and analysis for all difference applications should be conducted with constant attention.

A major concern regarding nanoparticles is that they might not be detectable after release into the environment, which in turn can create difficulties if remediation is needed. Therefore, analysis methods need to be developed to detect nanoparticles in the environment that accurately determine the shape and surface area of the particles (two of the factors that define their toxic properties).

- More information is needed regarding the structure-function relationships and in relating surface area and chemistry to functionality and toxicity.
- Full risk assessments should be performed on new nanomaterials that present a real risk of exposure during manufacture or use. Such assessments should take into consideration the toxicological hazard, the probability of exposure and the environmental and biological fate, transport, persistence, transformation into the finished product and recycling.
- Life cycle analysis will be a useful tool for assessing the true environmental impacts.
- When the use of scarce material is inevitable for the elaboration of the nanoparticles, an effective strategy for recycling and recovery is necessary.

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